

Table 1. List of arthropods identified, total captures and percentage associated of total captures by the three different trapping systems. The unidentified arthropods were indicated with the acronym of NPI (Not Possible Identification). (GT-ECO Ground trap with EcoSordidina; PT-GEL pitfall trap with Cosmogel; PT-PLUS Pitfall trap with Cosmoplus).

Class	Order	São Bento					São Pedro				
		%	TOT	PT-GEL	PT-PLUS	GT-ECO	%	TOT	PT-GEL	PT-PLUS	GT-ECO
Malacostraca	Isopoda	20,30	1882	995	866	21	10,49	969	488	417	64
	Amphipoda	2,03	188	131	42	15	2,80	259	116	36	107
	Diplopoda	1,46	135	39	87	9	1,82	168	97	53	18
	Chilopoda	0,02	2	0	0	2	0,24	22	12	2	8
	Gasteropoda	0,54	50	16	22	12	3,25	300	86	154	60
Arachnida	Araneae	0,67	62	21	25	16	1,72	159	51	39	69
	Opilionidae	0,06	6	2	1	3	0,08	7	3	4	0
	Pseudoscorpionidae	0,32	30	13	13	4	0,91	84	53	24	7
Hymenoptera	Adults	0,29	27	16	7	4	0,37	34	18	7	9
	Formicidae	2,98	276	102	151	23	3,12	288	118	106	64
	Dermaptera	0,15	14	9	5	0	0,10	9	8	1	0
	Rynchota	0,43	40	20	18	2	0,69	64	44	11	9
Coleoptera	<i>Cosmopolites sordidus</i>	33,76	3130	926	1863	341	45,40	4192	1454	1973	765
	Staphylinidae	15,47	1434	683	732	19	12,90	1191	574	562	55
	Carabidae	0,81	75	45	26	4	0,82	76	49	19	8
	Other adults	0,53	49	25	18	6	0,64	59	39	10	10
	Larvae	0,99	92	80	12	0	3,75	346	338	8	0
Diptera	Other adults	0,98	91	29	27	35	3,63	335	88	160	87
	Other pupae	0,00	0	0	0	0	0,10	9	3	6	0
	Tipulidae (larvae)	0,12	11	0	11	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Tipulidae (Pupae)	0,05	5	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Culicidae (larvae)	0,00	0	0	0	0	1,17	108	0	108	0
	Culicidae (Pupae)	0,01	1	0	1	0	0,03	3	0	3	0
	Psychodidae (Larvae)	15,70	1456	460	996	0	4,45	411	55	356	0
	Psychodidae (Pupae)	2,15	199	58	141	0	1,10	102	1	101	0
	Syrphidae (Larvae)	0,02	2	1	0	1	0,04	4	2	0	2
Psocoptera		0,01	1	0	0	1	0,01	1	0	0	1
Lepidoptera	Adults	0,04	4	1	1	2	0,03	3	1	2	0
	Larvae	0	0	0	0	0	0,04	4	4	0	0
	Orthoptera	0,01	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Trichoptera		Larvae	0	0	0	0	0	0,01	1	0
	Thysanoptera	0,01	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	NPI	0,09	8	7	0	1	0,28	26	13	9	4
Total			9272	3680	5071	521		9234	3715	4171	1348

Different letters indicate difference between treatments (LMM, least-square means method, $p < 0.05$).